

Complex Ammoniacal Cobalt Molybdates.

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The preparation and properties of the complex cobalti-ammine molybdates have not been much studied evidently due to the nature of molybdate radicle, easily condensing into *iso*-poly complexes like di- and trimolybdates, which give rise to much complications. A cobalti-ammine molybdate of the empirical formula $Co_2O_3 \cdot 7MoO_3 \cdot 10NH_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ has been described by Carnot (*Compt. rend.*, 1889 109, 112); no definite constitution has been ascribed to the compound. The only noteworthy investigation in the subject has been made by Paul and Sarkar (*Ann. Chim.*, 1926, 5, 119). They have prepared and studied a large number of molybdates and polymolybdates of complex tetrammine cobaltic ion. Further, they have obtained evidences in a few cases where the molybdate or dimolybdate radicle forms a part of the cobaltic complex. In the case of pentammine series they succeeded in preparing one trimolybdate, one molybdate and one heptamolybdate of aquopentammine cobaltic complex. In the case of the tetrammine series they started either with the carbonatotetrammine cobaltic nitrate or the pure aquotetrammine cobaltic nitrate which by double decomposition with the normal sodium molybdate or sodium dimolybdate or ammonium molybdate gave the various compounds. In the case of the pentammine series also similar methods were followed. The present investigation was undertaken in order to make a more detailed study of the subject under conditions which would avoid complications due to the formation of *iso*-poly-complexes by the molybdate radicle itself and thus would give rise to more well-defined compounds of normal molybdates free from the impurities of di- and trimolybdates.

The method adopted differed entirely from that of Paul and Sarkar. A mixture of the cobalt salt and normal sodium molybdate or molybdic acid in presence of calculated quantities of ammonium salt and ammonia was oxidised by the passage of a vigorous current of air through the solution, the crystals obtained were further purified by

repeated crystallisation from ammoniacal solution—thus preventing the formation of any polymolybdates. Barring two instances in which the normal molybdate radicle seemed to enter the complex, all the other compounds obtained were normal cobalti-ammine molybdates. The compounds obtained can be represented by the following constitutional formulae.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Chloropentammine Cobaltic Molybdate (I).

Hydrated cobalt chloride (10 g.) was dissolved in water and to the resulting solution ammonium chloride (15 g.) was added, water being added in such quantity as to leave a portion of ammonium chloride undissolved. To this mixture, crystallised normal sodium molybdate (20 g.) made into a thin paste with water was stirred in (sodium molybdate was prepared by dissolving solid molybdic acid in caustic soda solution in stoichiometric proportions, filtering, evaporating the filtrate to a small bulk, draining away the mother-liquor and finally washing the crystals with alcohol to remove free alkali). To the mixture 70 c.c. of concentrated ammonia (d 0.9) were added. The mixture was kept at 15-20° and a rapid current of air was drawn in through the mixture till all solids dissolved. It was then filtered and

air was passed for four hours more. The mixture was then kept overnight in an ice-chest. Next day air was again passed for 5-6 hours more, by which time copious rose-red crystals separated. After allowing to settle for some time the mixture was filtered and the crystals were washed with 20% (by vol.) alcohol containing 2% ammonia and finally with absolute alcohol.

This substance could not be recrystallised. It was freely soluble in pure water when freshly prepared, but on attempting to evaporate the solution either on the water-bath, in air, or in vacuum, it decomposed. It was also freely soluble in ammoniacal water and from the solution a purple crystalline substance slowly separated which was insoluble in water. It was decomposed even by very dilute acids with the separation of free molybdic acid. It could not be salted out by a saturated solution of ammonium chloride as molybdate (MoO_4) group would be replaced by chlorine. With ammonium molybdate solution a gelatinous precipitate was obtained.

On the addition of alcohol to an ice-cold aqueous solution of the substance in the absence of ammonia a precipitate was obtained. But on an attempt to redissolve, it was found to be partly insoluble. On keeping for some weeks this precipitate was wholly converted into an insoluble variety identical with the insoluble product obtained from an ammoniacal solution. Treatment with aqueous alcohol at the room temperature led to the decomposition of the substance with separation of molybdic acid.

On analysis the crude compound gave the following results: Co, 17.6; MoO_4 , 32.28; Cl, 18.5; NH_3 , 25.9; H_2O , 5.8 per cent. corresponding to $\text{Co}_3(\text{NH}_3)_{15}\text{Cl}_5(\text{MoO}_4)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The composition was however found to vary slightly in different preparations.

In solution it gave neutral reaction with litmus. Silver nitrate with dilute nitric acid in the cold gave with the solution of the freshly prepared substance at once a curdy white precipitate of silver chloride; the filtrate on heating gives further a very small quantity of silver chloride. Lead acetate acidified with a single drop of dilute acetic acid at once gave a precipitate of lead molybdate in the cold, the precipitate was difficult to filter; the filtrate on heating remained clear. The substance was found to belong to the pentammine series as it gave carmine-red crystals of chloropentammine chloride on evaporation with strong hydrochloric acid after the previous removal of molybdic acid by lead acetate and produced a red crystalline precipitate with ammonium oxalate. This crude substance on treatment

with dilute ammonia gave two products as described later on—the insoluble chloropentammine cobaltic molybdate (I) and the soluble hydroxopentammine cobaltic molybdate (II). From the behaviour of the substance it may be assumed that it is probably a mixture of

in the approximate proportion of 1 : 2. The compound (ii) in solution, specially in presence of ammonia, gradually changes as follows :

The presence of ammonia helps to shift the equilibrium completely to the right by the removal of hydrochloric acid. All attempts to prepare the pure aquopentammine chloromolybdate were unsuccessful on account of this partial dissociation. Attempt at separation in an acid medium on the other hand led to the separation of molybdic acid.

To a saturated aqueous solution of the rose-red mother-substance a few drops of ammonia were added, when a small quantity of purple crystals separated out. These were washed with water and dried in air. (Found: Co, 17·00; MoO₄, 47·82; Cl, 10·22; NH₃, 25·3. [Cl·Co·(NH₃)₅] MoO₄ requires Co, 17·38; MoO₄, 47·18; Cl, 10·46; NH₃, 25·03 per cent.).

This new substance had a deep purple colour and was insoluble in water. It gave very well-defined crystals. On shaking with silver nitrate in the cold the substance gradually went into solution yielding a white precipitate of silver molybdate soluble in dilute nitric acid, on warming the filtrate a curdy white precipitate of silver chloride was formed showing that the chlorine is inside and the molybdate radical is outside the complex zone. The substance gave carmine-red crystals of chloropentammine chloride on evaporation with concentrated hydrochloric acid. Hence the substance was found to be a chloropentammine molybdate.

Hydrozopentammine Cobaltic Molybdate (II).

On adding alcohol to the filtrate of the previous compound a precipitate was obtained; this was allowed to settle in a cold place and filtered. It was then dissolved in a small quantity of 4% ammonia and reprecipitated with alcohol. This was repeated once more. It was washed with 30% alcohol containing ammonia and finally with absolute alcohol. The red crystals obtained were dried over sulphuric acid. (Found: Co, 17.0; MoO₄, 48.49; NH₃, 25.1. [OH·Co·(NH₃)₅]MoO₄·H₂O requires Co, 17.41; MoO₄, 47.2; NH₃, 25.07 per cent.).

The substance was found to be readily soluble in water and strongly alkaline to litmus. Lead acetate gave immediately a precipitate of lead molybdate in the cold—the filtrate yielded no further precipitate on acidification with a drop of acetic acid and heating. On removal of molybdenum with lead acetate, and of lead with excess of hydrochloric acid and evaporation of the resulting solution on the water-bath, carmine-red crystals of chloropentammine cobaltic chloride were obtained. These reactions proved it to be a hydroxopentammine cobaltic molybdate.

The same substance—but in a different state of hydration—was also obtained in the following way:

Hydrated cobalt nitrate (10 g.) and ammonium nitrate (22 g.) were dissolved together in the least quantity of water. Sodium molybdate (20 g.) was dissolved in strong ammonia (100 c.c.). The two solutions were mixed and filtered, cooled to 15° and into the solution a brisk current of air was passed till the black crystals of oxycobaltic compounds appeared. Then the mixture was heated to 40° and oxidation by air was continued till the black crystal disappeared giving rise to the formation of a red crystalline deposit. It was then left overnight in an ice-chest. Next day air was passed for two to three hours more; and the mixture was allowed to settle in a cool place and filtered. The red crystals obtained were washed with 30% alcohol containing 1% ammonia. For recrystallisation the mass was dissolved in 4% ammonia at 60°, the solution was cooled and a few drops of alcohol were added to induce crystallisation. It was then left in the ice-chest. Large silky crystalline plates were obtained; these were washed as before and dried in air to a constant weight. (Found: Co, 16.02; MoO₄, 43.45; NH₃, 23.19. [OH·Co·(NH₃)₅]MoO₄·2½H₂O requires Co, 16.12; MoO₄, 43.71; NH₃, 23.22 per cent.).

On drying over sulphuric acid for three weeks it lost two molecules of water. This was found to be a better method of preparing this compound.

Aquopentammine Cobaltic Molybdate (III) and Molybdatopentammine Cobaltic Molybdate (IV).

Hydrated cobalt acetate (10 g.), made into a paste with 10 c.c. water and a little dilute acetic acid, was dissolved in 30 c.c. of concentrated ammonia (*d* 0.9). Ordinary crystallised ammonium molybdate (20 g.) was dissolved in 60 c.c. of concentrated ammonia. The two solutions were mixed and filtered. The filtrate was cooled to about 20° and a rapid current of air was drawn through it. Copious black crystals of oxycobalt-compounds separated after sometime, the temperature was then raised to 30-40° and ultimately to 50° and maintained at that point till all the black crystals disappeared and a large amount of a red crystalline substance separated. The mixture was then cooled to 10° and the oxidation by air was continued for sometime more. It was then allowed to settle in a cool place and filtered. The crystals were washed with dilute alcohol containing one per cent. ammonia. For recrystallisation the substance was dissolved in 10% ammonia at 70°, the solution was cooled and crystallisation was induced by adding alcohol. The crystals were filtered and washed with cold 1% ammonia and alcohol and dried in air. (Found: Co, 14.57; MoO₄, 59.76; NH₃, 21.22. [H₂O·Co(NH₃)₅]₂(MoO₄)₃ requires Co, 14.68; MoO₄, 59.70; NH₃, 21.14 per cent.). It was fairly soluble in water and the solution was very faintly alkaline to litmus. This indicates that the substance is slightly hydrolysed by water as follows:

The hydroxo-compound evidently being more alkaline masks the weak acid character of molybdic acid. Lead acetate or silver nitrate at once precipitated all the molybdenum in the cold. On heating to 100° it lost very little water but on gradually raising the temperature it was found to lose one molecule of water at 125-130° thus passing into a complex molybdatomolybdate. The dehydrated product was sparingly soluble in water, and when shaken with silver nitrate solution gave a precipitate of silver molybdate in the cold and the

filtrate on treating with a few drops of acetic acid and boiling gave a further precipitate of silver molybdate proving that a part of the molybdate radicle remained in the complex cation.

Paul and Sarkar (*loc. cit.*) described an insoluble aquopentamine cobaltic molybdate which in the light of the present work appears to be a hydrated molybdato-pentamine molybdate. Lead acetate and nitrate solutions, as have been found, cannot decompose the insoluble molybdato-pentamine molybdate and hence no molybdic acid could be detected in the filtrate after treating the compound with lead nitrate or acetate solution. This is possibly the reason why Paul and Sarkar supposed the insoluble compound to be an aquo-salt. It is more likely that Paul and Sarkar's compound contained no water at all. The insoluble compound is therefore proved to be a molybdato-pentamine molybdate $[\text{MoO}_4 \cdot \text{Co} (\text{NH}_3)_5]_2 \text{Mo}_4 \text{O}$.

On prolonged digestion with water it passes into the aquopentamine molybdate and goes into solution.

*Aquanitrotetrammine Cobaltic Molybdats (V) and
Nitrotetrammine Molybdato-cobalt (VI).*

Hydrated cobalt acetate (10 g.) was triturated with 10 c.c. of water and a few drops of dilute acetic acid. This was then dissolved in 20 c.c. of concentrated ammonia (d 0.9). Sodium nitrite (3 g.) was dissolved in this solution, to which 7 g. of molybdic acid dissolved in conc. ammonia (60 c.c.) were added. The mixture was filtered. The filtrate was cooled to 15° and a rapid current of air was drawn through it till the black crystals of oxycobalt compounds appeared. Temperature was then raised to 25° and air was passed till all the black crystals disappeared. It was left overnight in an ice-chest, and air was passed again through the cold solution next day till copious red crystals separated. It was allowed to settle and then filtered. For recrystallisation the mass was dissolved in 6% ammonia and allowed to evaporate in air at the room temperature. The crystals separated were washed with 1% cold ammonia. (Found: Co, 16.63; MoO_4 , 44.81; NH_3 , 19.72; N, 19.95. $[\text{NO}_2(\text{NH}_3)_4 \cdot \text{Co} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}] \text{MoO}_4$ requires Co, 16.81, MoO_4 , 45.58; NH_3 , 19.37; N, 19.95 per cent.)

The light red-coloured substance was found to be sparingly soluble in water. The whole of the molybdate radicle was precipitated in the cold by neutral lead nitrate or silver nitrate solution, proving

the molybdate radicle to be outside the complex zone. On heating to about 96° in a steam-oven it lost one molecule of water and became more sparingly soluble. The colour of the crystals also became slightly dull. Evidently the dehydrated product was a nitro-tetrammine molybdatocobalt of the formula,

But on digesting it with either neutral lead nitrate or silver nitrate solution the whole of the molybdate was removed. It, therefore, indicates that the substance is easily hydrolysed in water into original aquonitrotetrammine cobaltic molybdate as follows:—

Thiocyanatopentammine Cobaltic Molybdate (VII).

Cobalt acetate crystals (10 g.) were dissolved in 10 c.c. of water and 20 c.c. of concentrated ammonia (*d* 0.90); to this was added a solution of ammonium thiocyanate (4 g.) in 10 c.c. of water. A solution of ammonium molybdate (8 g.) was made in strong ammonia (70 c.c.) and the two solutions were mixed and filtered. The filtrate was cooled and a rapid current of air was drawn through it. Black crystals of oxycobalt compounds separated as before when the temperature was raised to 30-40°. These then gradually disappeared. The solution was then left overnight in a cool place. Next day air was passed again through the solution at 10° when large quantities of red crystals separated. The mixture was then filtered after allowing it to settle in a cool place. The substance was purified by recrystallisation from 6% ammonia at 60°. The crystals obtained were washed with cold 1% ammonia and dried in air. (Found: Co, 15.97; MoO₄, 43.86; NH₃, 22.79; SCN, 15.57; [SCN·Co·(NH₃)₅] MoO₅ · $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O requires Co, 15.91; MoO₄, 43.12. NH₃, 22.91; SCN, 15.63 per cent.). Another sample dried in air to a constant weight gave Co, 16.14. [SCN·Co·(NH₃)₅]MoO₄ requires Co, 16.30 per cent.; so that the latter is anhydrous.

The dark red crystals were found to be sparingly soluble in water and neutral to litmus. On digesting the substance with silver nitrate

solution in the cold the whole of the molybdate and the thiocyanate were removed indicating that the substance readily hydrolysed in water into an aquopentammine cobaltic thiocyanatomolybdate,

Nitratopentammine Cobaltic Molybdate (VIII).

Hydrated cobalt nitrate (10 g.) was dissolved in water (20 c.c.) and ammonium nitrate (4 g.) was added to it. Ammonium molybdate (7 g.) dissolved in 60 c.c. of ammonia (*d* 0.9) was then added and the mixture was filtered rapidly. The filtrate was cooled to 20° and a rapid current of air was drawn through it till black crystals of oxycobalt compounds separated out. Temperature was then raised to 40° and the passage of air-current was continued till all the black particles disappeared. It was then filtered and left overnight. Next day air was again passed through the cold solution till copious red crystals separated. The mixture was then filtered after allowing to settle in a cool place. For recrystallisation it was dissolved in 6% ammonia at 60° and allowed to evaporate spontaneously in air. The crystals separated were washed first with cold 20% alcohol containing ammonia and finally with absolute alcohol. They were then dried in the air. (Found: Co, 16.01; MoO₄, 43.99; NH₃, 23.01; N, 22.91. [NO₃ · Co · (NH₃)₅]MoO₄ requires Co, 16.12; MoO₄, 43.71; NH₃, 23.22; N, 22.95 per cent.).

The substance was found to be soluble in water and neutral to litmus. Lead acetate immediately precipitated the whole of the molybdenum in the cold proving it to be a nitratopentammine cobaltic molybdate.

Method of Analysis.

In the above compounds cobalt was always estimated volumetrically. The compounds were decomposed by digesting on the water-bath with excess of pure caustic soda, and the cobaltic oxide, after being thoroughly washed free from alkali was treated with potassium iodide solution and acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard thiosulphate. The filtrate was treated with excess of liquor ammonia and then saturated with sulphuretted hydrogen. On acidification and being heated on the

water-bath the molybdenum was precipitated as sulphide; it was filtered, washed converted into trioxide by ignition and weighed as such. Chlorine was estimated as silver chloride in the filtrate from molybdenum, after removing the sulphuretted hydrogen by evaporation and treatment with ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide. Ammonia was always estimated by distillation with caustic soda. Total nitrogen was estimated by combustion. To estimate the thiocyanate group the compound was broken up with pure caustic soda, and the filtrate was treated with hydrogen peroxide to oxidise the thiocyanate; molybdenum was then precipitated, after neutralising the solution carefully with nitric acid, by excess of silver nitrate; and the excess of silver was removed by hydrochloric acid, and in the filtrate sulphur was precipitated by barium chloride after the removal of nitric acid by evaporation with hydrochloric acid.

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